

Short name	Risk and benefit perceptions	Long name	Status of knowledge on public perceptions of risks and benefits of CCUS
Geographical scope	There is considerable research into public perceptions of CCUS focuses on research in European nations (either single countries or comparative) but there is no universal alignment between these different studies that would allow inferring generally higher or lower ratios of benefit-risk perception in the general population. North American and East Asian nations are also regularly represented in the research literature.		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>Numerous studies show evidence that the perception of risks and benefits is inversely correlated. The low perceived benefits of proposed infrastructures often enhance any concerns over possible risks.</p> <p>Nearly all research on public perceptions of CCUS examines beliefs about risks and benefits attributed to the technology and its implementation¹. Over a multitude of studies, key risks of CCUS have been identified as:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CCUS only addressing symptoms of problematic carbon emissions and not the causes^{2,3}, 2. Incentivization of CCUS leading to reduced policy incentives to mitigate carbon emissions further (“mitigation deterrence”), 3. Safety concerns over physical leaks of CO₂ or explosions due to over-pressurisation, 4. High cost/expenses of the technology resulting in public expenditure or rising product prices⁴, 5. Physical uncontrollability of the technology, and 6. Public and scientific uncertainty about the technology⁵. <p>Benefits that are often mentioned include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reducing carbon emissions, thereby mitigating climate change^{2,6,7}, and 2. Economic investment in jobs and communities where projects occur. <p>Trust in institutional actors responsible for implementing or regulating projects is regularly revealed as the most important factor that shapes both risk and benefit perceptions⁸. Trust reliably has a much larger effect on risk and benefit perceptions than knowledge of CCUS does⁹.</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	Public perceptions research commonly alleges that risk and benefit perceptions are key determinants of support for CCUS, with benefit beliefs being seen as more important for predicting support and acceptance to CCUS generally, and risk beliefs being seen as more important in relation to acceptance of specific local projects ⁹ .		
Other issues this affects	Public support for CCUS, public engagement with CCUS, communication about CCUS, cross-national comparisons of CCUS perceptions		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tcvetkov, P., Cherepovitsyn, A., & Fedoseev, S. (2019): Public perception of carbon capture and storage: A state-of-the-art overview. <i>Heliyon</i>, 5(12), e02845. • Cox, E., Spence, E., & Pidgeon, N. (2020): Public perceptions of carbon dioxide removal in the United States and the United Kingdom. <i>Nature Climate Change</i>, 10(8), 744-749. 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bellamy, R. (2022): Mapping public appraisals of carbon dioxide removal. <i>Global Environmental Change</i>, 76, 102593. • Karimi, F., & Komendantova, N. (2017): Understanding experts' views and risk perceptions on carbon capture and storage in three European countries. <i>GeoJournal</i>, 82(1), 185-200. • Broecks, K., Jack, C., Ter Mors, E., Boomsma, C., & Shackley, S. (2021): How do people perceive carbon capture and storage for industrial processes? Examining factors underlying public opinion in the Netherlands and the United Kingdom. <i>Energy Research & Social Science</i>, 81, 102236. • Karimi, F., Toikka, A., & Hukkinen, J. I. (2016): Comparative socio-cultural analysis of risk perception of Carbon Capture and Storage in the European Union. <i>Energy Research & Social Science</i>, 21, 114-122. • Satterfield, T., Nawaz, S., & St-Laurent, G. P. (2023): Exploring public acceptability of direct air carbon capture with storage: climate urgency, moral hazards and perceptions of the 'whole versus the parts'. <i>Climatic Change</i>, 176(2), 14. • Parmiter, P., & Bell, R. (2020): Public perception of CCS: A Review of Public Engagement for CCS Projects. 2nd Report of the Thematic Working Group on: Policy, Regulation and Public Perception. CCUS Project Network. • Evensen, D. (2022): Public perceptions of carbon capture, use, and storage (CCUS). <i>Oxford Energy Forum</i>, 130, 21-24.
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^[1] Tcvetkov, P., Cherepovitsyn, A., & Fedoseev, S. (2019). Public perception of carbon capture and storage: A state-of-the-art overview. *Heliyon*, 5(12), e02845.

^[2] Cox, E., Spence, E., & Pidgeon, N. (2020). Public perceptions of carbon dioxide removal in the United States and the United Kingdom. *Nature Climate Change*, 10(8), 744-749.

^[3] Bellamy, R. (2022). Mapping public appraisals of carbon dioxide removal. *Global Environmental Change*, 76, 102593.

^[4] Karimi, F., & Komendantova, N. (2017). Understanding experts' views and risk perceptions on carbon capture and storage in three European countries. *GeoJournal*, 82(1), 185-200.

^[5] Broecks, K., Jack, C., Ter Mors, E., Boomsma, C., & Shackley, S. (2021). How do people perceive carbon capture and storage for industrial processes? Examining factors underlying public opinion in the Netherlands and the United Kingdom. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 81, 102236.

^[6] Karimi, F., Toikka, A., & Hukkinen, J. I. (2016). Comparative socio-cultural analysis of risk perception of Carbon Capture and Storage in the European Union. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 21, 114-122.

^[7] Satterfield, T., Nawaz, S., & St-Laurent, G. P. (2023). Exploring public acceptability of direct air carbon capture with storage: climate urgency, moral hazards and perceptions of the 'whole versus the parts'. *Climatic Change*, 176(2), 14.

^[8] Parmiter, P., & Bell, R. (2020). Public perception of CCS: A Review of Public Engagement for CCS Projects. 2nd Report of the Thematic Working Group on: Policy, Regulation and Public Perception. CCUS Project Network.

^[9] Evensen, D. (2022). Public perceptions of carbon capture, use, and storage (CCUS). *Oxford Energy Forum*, 130, 21-24.